

INDOOR AIR POLLUTION: OXIDATIVE CAPACITY OF INDOOR ENVIRONMENT AND IMPACT ON HUMAN HEALTH

Onwukwe, C.O.S.^{*1}, Ogbuokiri O.A.C.¹ and Ibemere, L.C.¹

¹ Department of Architecture, Federal Polytechnic Nekede-Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Corresponding author's email: sonwukwe@fpno.edu.ng; elixirdesign2002@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Indoor Air Pollution is a phenomenon that has continuously proven to be of major quagmire to the Built Environment irrespective of where the building envelope is domiciled. Every geographic region has its challenges of air pollutants that are peculiar to the emerging technology and society revolving around its population. This scientific review seeks to identify these pollutants, their payload, sources and effects on the metabolism of occupants. Further expository analysis showed the subgroups of these pollutants which, in some cases, identified that some pollutants belong to multiple subgroups. In addition, this paper brought to knowledge latent photo-oxidation cycles where hydroxyl radical (OH) oxidize primary volatile organic compounds (VOCs) creating tropospheric ozone (O₃), secondary TVOCs and secondary organic aerosols (SOAs) which further impoverish Indoor Air Quality (IAQ). Anchorage is on the discourse surrounding two major building-associated illnesses: Sick Building Syndrome (SBR) and Building Related Illnesses (BRI). Indicators of these two major concerns are fully elucidated paving way for further studies into cost-effective ways of proffering viable solutions.

Keywords: Built Environment, Building Related Illness, Indoor Air Pollution, Ozone, Sick Building Syndrome.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Indoor environment conditions have contributed greatly to human wellbeing as it is the microenvironment in which most people spend the major fraction of their daily time (Rehfuess & Smith, 2019). Annually, over 3.8 million people die prematurely from illness attributable to the household air pollution caused by the inefficient use of solid fuels and kerosene for cooking (World Health Organization, 2021). Of this figure, 27% are fatalities associated with pneumonia, 18% from stroke, 27% from ischemic heart disease, 20% from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) while 8% from lung cancer. Indoor Air Pollution (IAP) can be generated inside homes or buildings through occupants' activities, such as cooking, smoking, use of electronic machines, use of consumer products, or emission from building materials (Vinh et al., 2018). Harmful pollutants inside buildings include carbon monoxide (CO), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), particulate matter (PM), aerosol, biological pollutants, and amplification sites. Study on air quality and control has taken center-stage in the Built Environment as recent events clearly point out the need to do so. Apart from spike in cardiac, pneumonic and bronchial ailments, the issue of the Covid-19 outbreak and accompanying lockdown scenarios contributed serious threat to the health of occupants. Poor IAQ indices can lead to building-associated illnesses and a wide range of ailments (Walter, 2010). IAP is a heterogeneous phenomenon with particulate and gaseous components. Such composition depends on immediate sources, emission rates, and fenestration and ventilation conditions. IAP can be effectively tackled by determining and identifying sources of pollutants, measurement of concentration as guided by IAQ standards, identifying the oxidative capacity of volumetric spaces and being informed of the extent of impact of these pollutants on the health of occupants. In this paper, we are bringing to the fore sources, characteristics and health effects of each identified IAP and discuss health issues and building-associated illnesses related to such issue. It is expected that this study will open up vistas for the control and reduction of pollutant concentrations and better IAQ hinged on promising strategies for monitoring and control of IAP in the future.

2.0 Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) and Indoor Air Pollution (IAP):

Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) is the volumetric percentage of pollutants in one cubic meter of ambient breathable air within indoor spaces. IAQ is known to affect the health, comfort, and well-being of building occupants. IAQ can degenerate through gaseous emissions (CO, [radon](#), TVOCs), suspended atmospheric [particulates](#), organic spores of flora and fauna, or any environmental stressor that can impede wellbeing of occupants. Source control, filtration, and the use of [ventilation](#) to dilute contaminants are the primary methods for improving IAQ in most buildings. IAQ can also be improved by regular cleaning of potential cesspools of dust. Determination of IAQ involves the collection of air samples, monitoring human exposure to pollutants, collection of samples on building surfaces, and computer modelling of air flow inside buildings.

[Indoor Air Pollution](#) (IAP) is a major health hazard in [developing countries](#). A major source of IAP is the burning of [coal](#), and [biomass](#) including wood, charcoal, [dung](#), or crop residue for heating and cooking.

IAQ in residential areas or buildings is significantly affected by three primary factors: (i) outdoor air quality, (ii) human activity in buildings, and (iii) building and construction materials, equipment, and furniture. Pollution clouds and fenestration issues have substantial influence on IAQ as these clouds have the tendency of moving into indoor spaces, most especially, when such spaces are not properly ventilated. Daily chores and metabolic functions can also deteriorate IAQ through the discharge of organic plumes, environmental tobacco smoke (ETS), pesticides/insecticides, cleaning solvents, suspended atmospheric particulates (SAP), suspended organic stressors (SOS), fibers and any other substances that trigger allergies. Occupants also create favorable conditions for the development of millions of molds, fungus, pollen, spores, bacteria, viruses, and insects, such as dust mites and roaches. In addition, electronic machinery, such as computer workstations, photocopiers, printing machines, and sundry electronic gadgets used in offices emit tropospheric ozone (O₃) and total volatile organic compounds. Common building materials, such as polyvinyl chloride (PVC) floor covering, parquet, linoleum, rubber carpet, adhesive, lacquer, paint, sealant, and particle board, can shed toxic compounds like alkanes, aromatic compounds, 2-ethylhexanol, etc.

Another approach to lowering the concentrations of IAP in building envelopes is to increase the amount of outdoor air coming indoors, provided that the outdoor pollution indices is lower than indoor pollution indices. In many low-income settlements, most living units may not have expensive HVAC systems and air-filtration systems to compensate for reduced/impeded ventilation requirements. To this end, proper handling of fenestration, incorporation of attic fans and orientation of facades along wind corridors increases outdoor-indoor ventilation rate (US EPA, 2021).

3.0 Pollutants in Indoor Air Environment:

There are twelve common indoor air pollutant sources. They fall into one of four categories: **BTEX**, **biological pollutants**, **combustion byproducts**, and **legacy pollutants**. These stressors have the capacity to alter the health, wellbeing and comfort of occupants. Some health effects may show up shortly after a single exposure, or years later after prolonged exposure.

3.1 Asbestos

Asbestos is a mineral fiber. It occurs naturally in rock and soil. Asbestos is a strong cellulite material with substantial heat resistance. It plays important role in the construction industry as it is used for finishes, insulation, roofing and can act as a very good fire-retardant.

3.2 Amplification Sites

These are contaminants produced by living things. They are found in areas where there is plenty of food and moisture content. Amplification sites harbor bacteria, viruses, pet dander/saliva, dust, mites, and pollen.

3.3 Carbon Monoxide

CO is quite dangerous as it is not easily perceived during the process of incomplete combustion of fossil fuels. Carbon monoxide can be quite fatal especially when inhaled in large volumes.

3.4 Traditional Biomass

Burning solid fuels such as wood or charcoal to cook or heat a building can contribute to poor IAQ. These cooking/heating methods are still used by many households worldwide.

3.5 Formaldehyde

Formaldehyde is present in form of an industrial protective coating of construction materials and domestic appliances. It acts as resinous layer for timber, wooden products and insulation sheaths. It is also used as stabilizers for adhesives, paints, aesthetic preservatives and all media for the control of insects and arachnids.

3.6 Lead (Pb)

Lead clouds can reduce the quality of ambient air in a number of ways. Often times people with persuasion for metal processing and handling of leaded fuel are most affected by lead. Once inhaled, lead can accumulate throughout the body, causing many adverse effects (WHO, 2021).

3.7 Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂)

Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂) is part of the highly reactive family of nitrogen oxide gases. NO₂ is emitted from combustion of heavy hydrocarbons used to power heavy-duty trucks and power generators. When combined in high levels with water in the atmosphere, it can form acid rain.

3.8 Pesticides

Pesticides and insecticides are used to check the proliferation of colonies of pests and arachnids. As a result, they are inherently toxic.

3.9 Radon (Rn)

Radon is a naturally occurring radioactive gas. It has no taste, color, or smell, making it very difficult to detect without specific radon testing equipment. Radon occurs naturally in minute amounts around subterranean units and basements which most times, serve as storage spaces. They are not considered major health issue though they can form in larger volumes in areas where foundations and floors are close to aquatic environments. Most radon exposure occurs indoors as radon gas becomes trapped inside after entering through cracks and holes in a building's envelope.

3.10 Indoor Particulate Matter

Particulate matter (PM) pollution is when ambient air is inundated with solid particles which could be breathable depending on the size of such particles. Some could be observed with the unaided eye as pollen, fine aggregates, dust and carcinogenic plumes while other are so minute that they can be visualized with the aid of a microscope. Particulate matter can be emitted directly from a source, but oftentimes, it is the result of a complex chemical reaction from pollutants emitted from burning fuels (USEPA, 2022). Permissible levels of PM indices in homes and workplaces vary from country to country depending on each country's Air Quality Index (AQI).

3.11 Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs)

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are gaseous effluences exuded from certain solids and liquid compounds. They can be a result of many common household products including paints, wood preservatives, aerosol sprays, cleansers and disinfectants, moth repellants, air fresheners, stored fuels, dry-cleaned clothing, and pesticides (USEPA, 2022).

3.12 Environmental Tobacco Smoke

ETS is smoke exhaled from smokers through lifestyle consumption and combustion of tobaccos contained in cigarettes and cigars. Contact with plumes can be said to be passive smoking where individuals that belong to the non-smoking class can still be affected by the carcinogenic contents of the smoke. ETS has been classified by the EPA as a Group A carcinogen with more than 7,000 substances.

Table 1: Pollutants: Classifications, sources and health impact. Red markers indicate associated sub-group

Pollutants	Sub-group				Sources	Health Impact
	BTEX	Biological pollutants	Combustion byproducts	Legacy pollutants		
Asbestos					Floor and ceiling tiles, plasters, adhesives, wallboard, roofing materials, fireproofing materials, and cement products.	(a). Asbestosis and Mesothelioma – a cancer of the membranes lining the chest and lung cavity and/or the abdominal cavity
Amplification Sites					Pollens, viruses, mold, bacteria, fungi, mildews, etc.	Hypersensitivity pneumonitis, allergic rhinitis.
Carbon Monoxide					Combustion of coal, gasoline, kerosene, oil, propane, or wood and charcoal grills.	Dull headache, weakness, dizziness, nausea or vomiting, shortness of breath, confusion and loss of consciousness.
Traditional Biomass					Wood-fuels, agricultural by-products and dung burned for cooking and heating purposes.	Biomass smoke exposure is associated with both acute respiratory illness and chronic lung disease in adults.
Formaldehyde					Certain manufactured wood products such as cabinets, furniture and laminate flooring.	Exposure to low levels of formaldehyde may irritate eyes, nose, throat, airways, or skin.
Lead (Pb)					Inhalation of lead particles generated by burning materials containing lead.	At high levels of exposure lead attacks the brain and central nervous system, causing coma and even death.
Nitrogen Dioxide (NO ₂)					Nitrogen oxides in outdoor air. NO ₂ can also form indoors when fossil fuels like natural gas are burned.	Research has linked NO ₂ to cardiovascular issues, lower birth weight in newborns and increased risk of premature death.
Pesticides					Mixtures of substances that are mainly used in public health protection programs in order to protect humans from vector-borne diseases.	Pesticides can cause stinging eyes, rashes, blisters, blindness, nausea, dizziness, diarrhea. Long-term exposures cause reproductive harm and disruption of the endocrine system
Radon (Rn)					The main source of indoor radon is decay of radium in the soil subjacent to a house.	Lung cancer and leukemia.
Indoor Particulate Matter					IPM can be generated through cooking, burning of candles and use of kerosene heaters/stoves.	Aggravation of coronary and respiratory ailments; premature death of people with heart or lung disease.
Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs)					VOCs are emitted by a wide array of products including paints and lacquers, pesticides and furnishings.	VOCs include a variety of chemicals that can cause eye, nose and throat irritation, headaches, dizziness and skin problems.
Environmental Tobacco Smoke					Environmental tobacco smoke (ETS) is generated by the combustion of tobacco products.	Lung Cancer, Heart Disease. ETS exposure has damaging effects on blood platelets (needed for clotting) and the endothelium (tissues lining the heart, blood vessels, lymph vessels, etc).

4. IAQ Standards and Guidelines (EPA and ASHRAE Standard):

Nigeria Air Quality Policies are based on research that UNEP conducted in 2015 in response to Resolution 7 of the UNEA 1. It describes country-level policies that impact air quality. As the country’s air quality policy matrix is not yet fully robust, this study is leveraged on EPA and ASHRAE standards for threshold values of admissible pollutants although these values vary between countries and organizations.

Table 2. Threshold values for pollutants

Pollutants	Threshold Limit Value
PM2.5	25 µg/m ³ , based on 24-hour data
CO	25 ppm for an 8-hour workday (American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists, 2022). 35 ppm for an 8-hour workday (The National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH), 2018)
CO ₂	5,000 ppm TLV-TWA* and 30,000 ppm TLV-STEL** (American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists, 2022)
Radon	As radon is carcinogenic, there are no safe levels of exposure. Yet, the EPA has set an action level of 4 pCi/L
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	The recommended threshold limit value is 10 ppm.
Formaldehyde	Note that its threshold limit value is 0.1 ppm TLV-TWA* and 0.3 ppm TLV-STEL**
Methylene chloride	It has an odor threshold of 250 ppm.
NO ₂	1-hour standard at the level of 100 ppb.

Source: EPA IAQ Standards and Guidelines (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2021)

5. Impact of Indoor Oxidation Chemistry on Human Health:

For the single fact that humans typically spend more than 85% of their time indoors, there is a need for real-time, continuous measurements of hydroxyl radicals, nitrate radicals, and other short-lived, highly reactive oxidants in representative indoor environments. The major indoor oxidants are thought to be *ozone (O₃)*, the *nitrate radical (NO₃)*, and the *hydroxyl radical (OH)*.

Figure 1. Formation pathways of OH radicals within indoor spaces. Re-modelled with explanatory notes from (Vinh, Duckshin, & Young-Chul, 2020)

Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), hydroperoxy radicals (HO₂), alkylperoxy radicals (RO₂) and chlorine atoms (Cl) may also be important indoor oxidants under certain conditions. Such oxidants 'alter' the mix of chemicals that building occupants inhale, dermally absorb and incidentally ingest. However, oxidation processes that occur indoors are poorly characterized, and many of the anticipated reaction products are yet to be identified. OH radical is a very important outdoor oxidant. It plays a central role in photo-oxidation cycles, oxidizing primary volatile organic compounds (VOCs) to form (a) ozone in the presence of NO₂, (b) secondary oxygenated VOCs, and (c) secondary organic aerosols (SOA) derived from the less-volatile oxidized organics. Typical outdoor daytime OH concentrations are on the order of 10⁶ cm⁻³. Solar insolation, incident within indoor spaces bring in ultraviolet spectrum which is largely attenuated thus limiting photolysis as a source of hydroxyl radical (OH). **Consequently, the ozonolysis of alkenes has been hypothesized to be the major pathway for indoor OH formation.** However, a recent study conducted in a school classroom in Marseille, France is forcing re-evaluation of OH as an indoor oxidant. This study measured OH radical

concentrations directly using laser-induced fluorescence with a fluorescent assay by gas expansion. The measured concentrations peaked in late afternoon at $1.8 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, an order of magnitude higher than that suggested by modeling and indirect studies. *Analysis of the results indicates that the photolysis of HONO (nitrous acid) makes a greater contribution to indoor OH than previously assumed.* Unvented or poorly-vented gas-fired appliances are a strong source of indoor NO_2 , which can react with water absorbed on indoor surfaces to generate HONO. The Marseille field campaign found that wavelengths between 340 and 405 nm were readily available within this indoor environment. It also found OH levels as high as $1.5 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ during periods of increased ventilation. This may be partially due to decreased scavenging of OH by VOCs emitted indoors. These results illustrate the value of real-time continuous OH measurements in indoor settings and indicate that OH radical chemistry may play a more important role in indoor oxidation processes than previously thought. There is also an additional factor to consider—human occupancy. It is only within the past decade that we have learned that human occupancy dramatically influences ozone levels, and hence the oxidative capacity of indoor atmospheres. Occupants can influence reactions of ozone with squalene and unsaturated fatty acids found on human skin surfaces (Sasho & Charles, 2013).

6.0 Effects of Indoor Air Pollution to Human Health:

This review will focus on two major issues as concerns building-associated illnesses.

6.1 Sick Building Syndrome (SBS)

The term "Sick Building Syndrome" (SBS) is used to describe situations in which building occupants experience acute health and comfort challenges that appear to be linked to time spent in a living unit with no identifiable cause of ailment. The complaints may be localized in a particular room or zone, or may be widespread throughout the entire building envelope.

Indicators of SBS include: (a) occupants exhibiting symptoms of discomfort, nausea, stress, loss of concentration and sensitivity to odours, (b) inexplicable cause of symptoms and (c) most of the occupants report relief soon after leaving the building.

6.2 Building Related Illness (BRI)

In contrast, the term "building related illness" (BRI) is used when symptoms of diagnosable illness are identified and can be attributed directly to airborne building contaminants. Indicators of BRI include: (a) building occupants complain of symptoms such as cough; chest tightness; fever, chills; and muscle aches, (b) definitive symptoms which have clearly identifiable causes and (c) complainants requiring prolonged recovery time after leaving the building. As SBS and BRI are linked with acute and immediate health concerns of occupants, they can be associated with the dissociative tendencies users especially when such users have experienced long duration of occupation. This is not to say that the latter are not serious health risks as both should be included in any comprehensive evaluation of a building's IAQ.

7. Conclusion:

In conclusion, pollutants have severe impact on the IAQ of building envelopes as deteriorating indices of IAQ presupposes that there would be spike in illnesses of occupants. IAPs: BTEX, biological pollutants, combustion byproducts, and legacy pollutants mainly originate as fallout from human activities in buildings; combustion, cleaning, adoption of certain building materials, operation of gadgets within indoor environments and transduction from outdoor spaces. These pollutants could be negligible at first instance but long-term and consistent exposure to these pollutants and inherent oxidation processes can cause significant changes in the metabolism of unsuspecting occupants. This led to the identification of two major categories of building-associated illnesses: sick building syndrome (SBS) and building related illness (BRI).

These authors are still fully engaged in further studies towards unravelling cost-effective ways of plugging the research gap centered on solving the aforementioned issues.

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